

Thermal Properties of Carbon Materials Reinforced Aluminum Composites Fabricated by Hot Pressing with Semi-liquid Phase

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Abstract

Carbon materials exhibit medium to high thermal conductivity and a range of coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) depending on their structure and shape. Two types of carbon reinforcements, carbon fiber and diamond, combined with metal matrices which have remarkable thermal properties like aluminum and copper, are mainly used for heat sink applications. Carbon fiber has anisotropic properties with a medium to high thermal conductivity (100-900W/mK) and low CTE ($-1.0 \times 10^{-6}/K$) in the longitudinal direction to the fiber, and low thermal conductivity (10 W/mK) and high CTE ($6.0 \times 10^{-6}/K$) in the transverse direction of the fiber. Diamond has isotropic properties with high thermal conductivity (TC) (1000-2000W/mK) and low CTE ($1.0 \times 10^{-6}/K$). Therefore the use of carbon fiber or diamond, with Al or Cu matrices, will lead to anisotropic or isotropic heat sink composite materials respectively. Whatever matrix and reinforcement type, matrix/reinforcement interface properties are critical to optimize final property of the composite material. In the case of an aluminum matrix composite, the presence of the alumina layer on the surface of each aluminum particles inhibits the direct contact of the aluminum particles with the carbon reinforcement and chemical reaction at the matrix/reinforcement interface.

Recently, Mizuuchi et al. have reported 552W/mK of thermal conductivity in Al-D50% composite,

which has no porosity and controlled chemical reactions at the Al/Diamond interface. This material has been fabricated by spark plasma sintering (SPS) process [1]. However, SPS equipment is still specific; therefore this process is not suitable for mass production at a low-cost.

Here, we address how to fabricate Al-chopped carbon fiber (Al-CCF) and Al-D composites by conventional hot pressing with a semi-liquid phase. In this process, a chemical reaction between the solid aluminum particles and carbon reinforcements through the liquid aluminum-silicon (Al-Si) alloy phase has been achieved. Reinforcements, CCF or D,

Fig. 1. SEM micrograph of Al-Si alloy in (Al+Al-Si5%)+CCF50% composite.

Fig. 2. Thermal conductivities of Al-CCF and Al-D composites as function of volume fraction of reinforcements.

were mixed with Al (melting point of 660°C) including 5vol.% of Al-Si(11.3at%) alloy composite powder (melting point of 584.6°C), and hot-pressed at the temperatures ranging from 600°C to 610°C, with 60 MPa of pressure, for 30 min. Relative density of fabricated composites was more than 99.7% due to the infiltration of the liquid phase of Al-Si alloy (white part) into slight spaces (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 2 shows the TC of Al-CCF and Al-D composites. Thermal conductivities of Al-CCF composite were different due to the CCF orientation, slightly increased in the longitudinal direction and decreased in the transverse direction. On the other hand, TC of Al-D composite reached 400 W/mK in a (Al+Al-Si5%)-D50% composite. This result shows that Al-D composite, which has remarkable TC, can be fabricated by the conventional hot pressing process at a low-cost.

Fig. 3 shows CTEs of Al-CCF and Al-D composites. CTE values of Al-CCF and Al-D composites

decrease with volume fraction of reinforcement. CTE of Al-CCF composite in the longitudinal direction of the CCF was lower than that of the Al-D composite, and reached $7.0 \times 10^{-6}/K$ in the (Al+Al-Si5%)-CCF50% composite.

TEM analysis has to be performed at the matrix/reinforcement interface for both CCF and D reinforcements in order to correlate the thermal properties of the aluminum matrix composite with this elaboration process and conditions.

Reference

- [1] K. Mizuuchi, K. Inoue, Y. Aguri, Y. Morisada, M. Sugioka, M. Tanaka, T. Takeuchi, J. Tani, M. Kawahara, Y. Makino. "Processing of diamond particle dispersed aluminum matrix composites in continuous solid-liquid co-existent state by SPS and their thermal properties", *Composites Part B*, vol.42, pp825-831, 2011